

Paper Electrophoresis in the Study and Separation of Oxalato Complexes of Some less Familiar Metals*

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Binary mixtures of oxalato complexes of Zr(IV), Fe(II), Fe(III), Ti(IV), Al(III), VO(II), UO₂(II) and Mo(IV) have been subjected to paper electrophoresis using oxalic acid or potassium oxalate as carrier electrolyte. Separations of several binary mixtures such as Ti(IV)-Al(III) have been successfully achieved. Simple salt of Zr(IV), Fe(III), Ti(IV), Al(III), VO(II), Mo(VI) and UO₂(II) when electrophorised, Al(III), Mo(VI), UO₂(II) and VO(II) form anionic complexes when oxalic acid or potassium oxalate is used as carrier electrolyte and move towards the anode, and the rest move as simple cation.

THE present communication deals with electrophoretic migration of some less common oxalato metal complexes using paper as supporting medium and separation of a few binary mixtures in potassium-oxalate or oxalic acid as carrier electrolyte.

Shukla¹ studied Rh(III) oxalato complex by paper electrophoresis and established the formation of oxalato complex of Rh(III) as $K_3[Rh(C_2O_4)_3]$. Wasp² separated niobium and tantalum oxalate complexes by paper electrophoresis using S and S No.—2043 paper with a potential gradient of 16 volts per cm. in 0.05M ammonium hydrogen citrate (pH = 3).

An attempt has been made to separate binary oxalato complex mixtures of Fe(II), Fe(III), Al(III), VO(II), UO₂(II), Ti(IV), Zr(IV) and Mo(IV) paper electrophoretically and successful separations of oxalato complexes of (1) Zr(IV) from Fe(II) and Fe(III), (2) Ti(IV) from Fe(II) and Al(III), (3) VO(II) from Fe(II), Fe(III) and Al(III) using 0.133N potassium-oxalate, Al(III) from Ti(IV) and VO(II) using 0.133N oxalic acid, and Mo(IV) from Zr(IV) using 0.1N oxalic acid as carrier electrolyte have been achieved. Partial separation of binary mixtures of VO(II)-Zr(IV), Ti(IV)-Zr(IV) and UO₂(II)-Ti(IV) has also been achieved in 0.1N oxalic acid as carrier electrolyte when their anionic complexes are electrophorised. It has been found that each of these oxalato complexes moves towards the anode, as they all are anionic complexes. When simple salt solutions of Fe(III), Al(III), Mo(VI), Zr(IV), Ti(IV), UO₂(II) and VO(II) as $FeCl_3$, $AlCl_3$, $(NH_4)_2MoO_4$, $ZrOCl_2$, Na_2TiO_3 , $UO_2(NO_3)_2$ and NH_4VO_3 are electrophorised in potassium oxalate or oxalic acid, Al(III), Mo(VI), VO(II) and UO₂(II) form anionic complexes and move towards the anode and the rest move as simple cation.

Experimental

Apparatus used for the separation was of Wieland and Fischer type horizontal electrophoretic instrument. Paper strips (1 cm × 34 cm) from Whatman paper No. 1 have been used as supporting medium. Various binary mixtures of oxalato complexes were used for the electrophoretic separations.

Preparation of some oxalato complexes used for our work and their elemental analysis :

$Fe[Fe(C_2O_4)_2]_3$ was prepared from $Fe(OH)_3$ and oxalic acid. Potassium trioxalatoferrate (III)⁴ was prepared from calculated amounts of $FeCl_3$ and $K_2C_2O_4$ at 0°. Potassium trioxalato aluminate (III)⁴ was prepared from calculated amounts of $Al(OH)_3$, $KH_2C_2O_4$ and $K_2C_2O_4$. Oxalato complex of vanadium⁵ was prepared by treating a vanadate solution with saturated oxalic acid. Uranyl oxalato complex⁶ was prepared from uranyl acetate, $K_2C_2O_4$ and oxalic acid. Potassium tetraoxalato zirconate (IV)⁷ penta hydrate was prepared from calculated amount of $ZrOCl_2 \cdot 8H_2O$, potassium oxalate and oxalic acid. Oxalato complex of Mo(IV) as $K_2[Mo_3O_4(C_2O_4)_3 \cdot 5H_2O]$ ⁸ was prepared from molybdenum hydroxide, oxalic acid and potassium hydroxide and complex titanil oxalate⁹ (Anal BDH) was used in our experiment.

Results of the chemical analysis of the prepared oxalato complexes are given in the Table I.

Development of electrophorogram :

After electrophoresis the electrophorogram was dried, the zones of the migrants were identified with the help of appropriate developing agents. The

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TABLE 1

Name of the complexes	% of Metal		% of Oxalate		% of Water	
	found	calcd.	found	calcd.	found	calcd.
$K_3[Al(C_2O_4)_3] \cdot 3H_2O$	5.75	5.837	18.93	19.04	3.78	3.894
$K_3[Fe(C_2O_4)_3] \cdot 3H_2O$	11.50	11.37	17.80	17.92	3.52	3.665
$(NH_4)_2[VO(C_2O_4)_2] \cdot 2H_2O$	16.02	16.16	28.15	27.96	5.65	5.718
$K_2(O = Ti(C_2O_4)_2) \cdot 2H_2O$	13.63	13.53	24.79	24.85	4.97	5.084
$K_4[Zr(C_2O_4)_4] \cdot 5H_2O$	13.25	13.22	51.36	51.08	12.80	13.06
$K_2[UO_2(C_2O_4)_2] \cdot 3H_2O$	40.97	41.16	15.16	15.22	3.02	3.113
$K_2[Mo_3O_4(C_2O_4)_3] \cdot 5H_2O$	12.14	12.23	11.01	11.23	2.197	2.296

TABLE 2

Binary oxalato mixtures	Carrier electrolyte	Separation sequences of migrants and the distance traversed by the zones in cm	Time
Zr(IV)-Fe(II)	0.133 N potassium oxalate	-: Zr(IV), Fe(II)+ 2.9 to 4.2 4.5 to 8.4	2½ hr
Zr(IV)-Fe(III)	"	-: Zr(IV), Fe(III)+ 1.5 to 3.6 3.8 to 7.2	"
Ti(IV)-Fe(II)	"	-: Ti(IV), Fe(II)+ 1.8 to 4.7 5 to 8	"
Ti(IV)-Al(III)	"	-: Ti(IV), Al(III)+ 1.8 to 4.7 5 to 8.5	"
VO(II)-Fe(II)	"	-: VO(II), Fe(II)+ 2.8 to 4.1 4.4 to 8	"
VO(II)-Fe(III)	"	-: VO(II), Fe(III)+ 1.9 to 3.6 4 to 7.5	"
VO(II)-Al(III)	"	-: VO(II), Al(III)+ 2.9 to 4.2 4.5 to 8.5	"
Ti(IV)-Al(III)	0.133 N oxalic acid	-: Ti(IV), Al(III)+ 0.2 to 1.9 2.3 to 5	"
VO(II)-Al(III)	"	-: VO(II), Al(III)+ 0.2 to 2.4 2.8 to 7	"
Mo(IV)-Zr(IV)	0.1 N oxalic acid	-: Mo(IV), Zr(IV)+ 1 to 2 3 to 4.8	3 hr
VO(II)-Zr(IV)	"	-: [VO(II), Zr(IV)]+ 0.8 to 2.5 2.5 to 5.5	"
Ti(IV)-Zr(IV)	"	-: [Ti(IV), Zr(IV)]+ 2.6 to 4.2 4.2 to 6.2	"
UO ₂ (II)-Ti(IV)	"	-: [UO ₂ (II), Ti(IV)]+ 1.7 to 2.8 2.6 to 4	"

specific reagent, employed and the colour of the bands are as follows :

Reagent used	Ions migrated	Colour of the band
Yellow ammonium sulphide	Fe(II) and Fe(III)	black
Alizarin red 'S'	Al(III) and Zr(IV)	red
Potassium ferrocyanide	UO ₂ (II)	brown
Hydrogen peroxide	VO(II)	yellow
Ammonium thiocyanate and stannous chloride	Mo(IV)	red

Separation sequences and position of migrating zone (front and rear) from the point of application after 2½ or 3 hr electrophoresis of mixtures are shown in the table 2, where '+' sign indicates the migration towards the anode, '-' sign towards the cathode, ':' sign indicates point of application of the migrating ions, and the ions within parenthesis, '[']' indicating overlapping slightly.

Potential gradient of 6.4 volts per cm was maintained in case of 0.133N oxalic acid and 5.1 volts per cm was maintained in case of 0.133N potassium oxalate for 2½ hr in both the cases. Potential gradient of 6.1 volts per cm was maintained in case of 0.1N oxalic acid for 3 hr.

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